

ISic1086

Fragment of a funerary inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Castronuovo di Sicilia

Provenance

Built into the wall on the south-west side of the Chiesa di S. Pietro,
Castronuovo di Sicilia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Castronuovo di Sicilia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 15 cm

Width 56 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to
2
: mm

Text

1. [---] α χάρε

Apparatus

IG suggests reading [-]ιδα χάρε, but the resolution of the traces before the first alpha

is not easy without autopsy

Translation (en)

[---] farewell!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492715

EDCS 39102244

PHI 140569

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0267 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Giustolisi, V. 1999. Petra: atlante delle antiche strutture rupestri dell'alta valle del Platani (Castronovo). Palermo. At 15 figs.1-3

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